

CAVE BACELINHO, ALVAIÁZERE – FROM SANTOS ROCHA TO THE NEW INVESTIGATIONS: THE CONSERVATION OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL IRON ARTEFACTS

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Resumo: A gruta do Bacelinho localiza-se no centro de Portugal, concelho de Alvaiázere, distrito de Leiria. Trata-se de uma cavidade aparentemente semiartificial, aberta no período clássico para a extração de minério e apresentando ocupações esporádicas ao longo dos tempos. Nos inícios do século XX, Santos Rocha, chamado a atenção por um dos habitantes, deu-lhe destaque pela intervenção de duas sondagens, tendo-a reconhecido como uma mina luso-romana (1853-1910). Somente após um século o sítio foi revisitado para dar lugar a um trabalho mais persistente. Nas intervenções arqueológicas levadas a cabo foram exumados vários objetos metálicos, provenientes das várias fases de ocupação. O fato desta cavidade ser extremamente húmida e possuir características ambientais muito específicas, que se refletiram na conservação dos objetos arqueológicos, levantou uma série de questões relativas ao processo de degradação dos metais e a sua integração metodológica conservativa no âmbito da arqueologia subaquática. Este artigo pretende expor resumidamente estas singularidades, tentando relaciona-las com o ambiente envolvente e o contexto arqueológico.

Palavras chave: Gruta, Conservação de metais, Ferro, Arqueologia subaquática

Abstract: The cave of Bacelinho is located in central Portugal, in the region of Alvaiázere. This is apparently a artificial cavity, originally excavated by the Romans for the mineral extraction. In the archaeological interventions carried out were exhumed several metal objects from the various timelines. This cavity is extremely wet and has very specific environmental characteristics which reflected in the conservation of archaeological objects and raised a number of questions regarding to the process of degradation of metals. These articles have the aim to expose these singularities, trying to relate them with the surrounding environment and the actual archaeological context.

Key-words: Cave; Metals preservation; Iron; Underwater Archaeology

Résumé: La grotte de Bacelinho est situé dans le centre du Portugal, dans la région de Alvaiázere. C'est apparemment une cavité artificielle, creusée à l'origine par les Romains pour l'extraction du minerai de fer et de rester à l'occupation occupations sporadiques au cours du temps. Dans les interventions archéologiques réalisées à ce jour, ont été exhumés de plusieurs objets métalliques des échéances diverses. Cette cavité est extrêmement humide et a caractéristiques environnementales spécifiques, qui ont été reflétées dans la conservation des objets archéologiques, a soulevé un certain nombre de questions relatives au processus de dégradation des métaux et leur intégration dans le cadre méthodologique de l'archéologie sous-marine. Cet article se propose d'exposer brièvement ces singularités, en essayant de les mettre en relation avec l'environnement et le contexte archéologique.

Mon-clé: Cave; La preservation des métaux; Fer; Archéologie sous-marine

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT

The place is a mine where the limestone is composed of iron oxide, given the cave reddish tinge. This factor, coupled with the fact of this cave being too wet, becomes the environment particularly interesting from the point of view of conservation of ferrous metals.

It must be pointed out that in these types of excavations, because of the environment, they should be treated with

methodologies that fit the theoretical and practical concepts of underwater archeology and conservation. So, the lack of understanding and use of these methods may result in the total destruction of the remains.

THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL PLACE

The Bacelinho Cave is composed of a wide space, arranged in three main halls and several galleries attached

Figure 1 – General plan of the cave showing the entrance area of the cavity, enclosed rooms and galleries

with a total size of more than 500 square meters. The internal environment has high moisture content, always over 90%. The soil is mostly silty, having two galleries completely submerged, with a depth that reaches 50 cm in winters. The entrance is relatively narrow, about 60 cm wide, facing south (figure 1).

Most rooms have signs of mining extraction. The main rooms were named Sala A, B and C and the galleries had a name as the features observed, like Fox Gallery (Galeria da Raposa), Maria Isabel (Galeria Maria Isabel), Pools (Galeria das Piscinas) and Chapels (Galeria das Capelas).

In all of them were checked material traces of the classical period. However, the observed higher percentage of artefacts recorded to the first room (sala A), led us to invest and focus our study in this area, during the year 2011, being from this space all the objects presented here.

This room had a set of stone structures that have the probably function of delimiting spaces, composed, in the upper zone, of a possible stakes or wooden planking, which supported a roof, in some places, made by *tegula* and *imbrex*. In these insides spaces we exhumed a lot of coals.

If we consider the moist environment in question, these roof structures serve to filter the water droplets fall observed on the walls and in the ceiling of the cavity.

In the zone further south we note a fireplace with a diameter greater than 1.20 cm and bordered by small stones. This fireplace has about 30 cm tall and is strategically positioned, getting the currents air that having access from the Fox gallery, which has also a small slit in contact with the outside, the southeast wall. This feature creates a small flow of air between the room A and the gallery, allowing the combustion and heat maintenance and the removal of carbon monoxide from the cavity, preventing intoxication.

Associated to the stone structures we recovered a wide variety of ceramic fragments, some in *sigilata*; fragments of glass containers, two flints, three natural crystals quartz and a number of metal objects that integrate between the Romans and medieval times (figure 3).

It was recovered more than thirty iron objects.

It was also exhumed a diversity of wildlife, especially the *sus scrofa*, *cervidae*, *ovis/capra* and some *ave* and *carnivora*.

This article aims, however, limit itself to the conservation treatment of the iron metals and analysis of particular pathologies recorded, with special emphasis on objects integrated in the classical period (II and III century AD).

From this time about the iron artefacts we highlight some fasteners, working mining (like iron wedge) and Roman

Figure 2 – The room layout with the detail of the stone structures, concentrating zone coals (squares B and C) and fireplace (grid A1)

Figure 3 – Excavated area with the spatial representation of the elements of glass, metal and lithic

Figure 4 – Drawing (a) and photo of Lucerne (b) (II and III century AD).

weaponry (arrowhead, spearhead, two swords and various *pilum*).

Among the elements that allow us to assess this chronology we include one Lucerne dedicated to Helios (the Sun God), with signs of use and possession of a small inscription on the base [LUCRECI] founded in the same level of this iron artefacts.

The different layers reported, considering that we are in a room with a sediment deposition traced by the entry run, are hardly noticeable. However it was considered two general stratigraphic levels, being the lowest the level that have the classical remains.

The metal objects are mostly spatially concentrated at the center of the room (squares C2, B2, B3 and C3), near of one roof abatement zone (considered by the presence of very fragments of *tegula* and *imbrex*) and concentration of carbon (derived probably from the destruction of the perishable structure that support the roof). It is noticeable especially the metal elements considered fastening founded around these patches of coal.

The swords are located in close proximity to one another. It is also noted that the sword from the grid C3 was registered under a *tegula* and both are integers.

Figure 5 – The room layout indicating the squares and metal artifacts recovered

METALS AND THEIR STATE OF CONSERVATION

Overall, almost all objects exhumed were very weak. The oldest layers showed large concretion, comprising iron oxides and scale of local rock.

The metals in general, but especially recorded in C and D squares bearing an abnormal condition where seemingly contrary to what is expected, there has been an iron deposit on the surface of the objects. Yet, despite this increase metal, the core was very weak. A concrete example of this situation is shown by swords, wherein the blade should not have more than 5mm thick, with variations in regions had 1 to 2 cm thick.

This increase in volume corresponds to no oxidation or layers of concretions in normal media objects from moist, but molten metal (figure 6) contrasting with the interior weak. The cause of this pathology is still unclear, however, consider that these objects have been accidentally exposed to high temperatures and, in this sense, some of the ore in this cave blew up, adding to the objects, then suffering deterioration by corrosion. This factor is supported by the high number of existing coal near the place where they were exhumed, and we can put in this case the hypothesis of a strong fire where focus structures already described.

Figure 6 – Detail of sword treated, which is visible the uneven caused by the increase of metal

Figure 7 – Wedge, after clean, where you can observe the deformation and small superficial blisters

Figure 8 – Arrowhead, after clean, where we can observe the small superficial blisters

Alongside this, it is still noteworthy, the type of corrosion. This is due to corrosion by bubbling hydrogen concentrations, one type of rare observation, creating deformations and very irregular appearance to the metal surface, resembling blistering or bubbling on the surface (figure 7 and 8). In the level of conservation, this disease causes inside crackers, leaving the metal very brittle (Eliaz *et al.*, 2002).

TREATMENT OF CONSERVATION

The treatments were based on the assessment of the conservation status of the metals, and based on the procedures used in the laboratory of Archaeology and Conservation of Submerged Heritage of Polytechnic Institute of Tomar (Portugal).

The intervention was based on three phases:

1. Cleaning – careful removal of layers of concretion. Were not removed the increments metal, except in one of the Roman swords, which, due to size and heavy weight of the increment was necessary to cut, using the grinder, part of the excess metal in order to restore balance and stability to the workpiece.
2. Stabilization – tempering treatment at high temperatures for removal of chlorides. The choice of this treatment is due to the fact that is a rapid and very effective method in eliminating them (Hamilton 1999). Having regard to the fragility of the metals, these were divided into two groups:
 - a. The most resistant were treated at temperatures of 750 degrees over a period of 24 hours;
 - b. The weakest were treated with temperatures of 400 degrees over a period of 48 hours.
3. Consolidation – collage of fragments, reinforcing and filling the gaps and areas for bonding with folder epoxy and fiberglass. Finally were insulated with graphite and microcrystalline wax.

CONCLUSIONS

As a conclusion we can infer that this cavity has been occupied not only as mine extraction, but also as a possible shelter, even during the classical times.

Like we know from others roman mines it were worked by probable slaves and guarded by military, detected by the presence of archaeological arms. Some of these objects may not only be combat weapons, but hunt objects.

Inside the cave there were found several fireplaces and a big diversity of small, medium or large fauna with traits of debones and kitchen. Probably the room A was served to eat and being the military room, since it is also close to the entrance.

The humidity contexts were the artefacts were found lead us to exhume and apply methodologies from underwater

Figure 9 – Sword, in iron, double-edged, before (a) and after (b) the conservation treatment, from the raster C2, level 2

Figure 10 – Sword, in iron, before (a) and after (b) treatment of conservation, from raster C3, level 2

Figure 11 – Buckle, in iron, before (a) and after (b) the conservation treatment, coming from the raster B3, level 2

archaeology, mainly the metal artefacts that came to us, characterized in a way almost unrecognizable, with huge fouling and concretions.

The perception of these traces is relatively complex, were only a careful view of this type of deteriorations and

Figure 12 – Nozzle arms, in iron, before (a) and after (b) the intervention. we can verify the amount of concretions and encrustations before the intervention

pathologies could allow its proper collection, survey and preservation, as well as its correct referral to a specialist underwater laboratory for conservation. In this sense, we consider important to warn the scientific community about the importance of the humid caves, often relegated from the scope of underwater archeology and excavated by inexperienced eyes of these contexts. In fact, in all traces recorded by Santos Rocha, in the early twentieth century, from this place, we not known descriptions, nor iron artefacts archived at the Santos Rocha Museum (Figueirada Foz, Central Portugal), founded by us in a quite large number, even in the surface.

These objects, full of concretions and encrustations and a highly weakened state, confound us with his own soil and cave rocks and can be easily damaged by archaeological works. We know that when exposed to these environments its suffer from irreversible destruction complex. The choices are few, and basically, the conservative process is limited to the stabilization of the object, trying to preserve as much of the information possible. The survey should be performed by collecting soil together with the object on which it is located, involving in a gauze or in a film adhesive and placing it in an airtight and stable container. After this first cares

made in field and the cleaning lab process, in the cases presented, since it are derived from a non-saline contexts, the tempering treatment proved to be a fast and effective method in the stabilization and elimination of chloride, allowing the subsequent consolidation and reconstruction of the objet and its further drawing and archaeological analysis.

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